

A Three Term-Empirical Equation for Low-Temperature Thermal Conductivity of Solids†

K. M. JHA*, M. L. THAKUR**, & S. P. JHA***

Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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Observed thermal conductivity of solids of various nature, i.e., metals, semiconductors and insulators including molecular crystals, at low temperatures, has been found to obey more closely a proposed three term equation as compared to that of the two term suggested earlier²⁻⁴, particularly for metals. The validity of the new equation in case of all the solids in general and the nature of the constants pertaining to the new equation have been found to give a strong support to the recent idea⁵ in respect of the predomination of phonons as the carriers of thermal energy in solids at low temperatures, $T < 0.3\theta$, θ being the Debye temperature.

OUR earlier analysis⁶ in respect of atomic heat and energy of solids suggests, (i) the mean free path of electrons and phonons to be the inverse function of a quantity like $(B+CT^2+DT^3)$, where B , C and D are constants⁶, and (ii) the thermal conductivity of solids at low temperatures, $T < 0.3\theta$, where θ is the Debye temperature, to be expressed by a three term equation. Some earlier views⁷⁻⁹ are also there to suggest a similar temperature variation of thermal conductivity in case of metals. However, no attempt was made to obtain the empirical constants pertaining to the equation⁷⁻⁹ and also to verify its validity in respect of the observed findings¹. The present communication is an attempt in this direction.

The equation for thermal conductivity, K , of solids which follows from the above suggestions⁶⁻⁹ may be written as :

$$K = \frac{T}{\alpha + \delta T^2 + \gamma T^3} \quad \dots (1)$$

where α , δ , and γ are constants. These constants are not strictly independent of each other rather each of them, more or less, is affected by change in the others. It may be mentioned here that the low temperature region, in which equation (1) is expected to be valid, is defined by $T \leq 0.3\theta$. Rearrangement of eqn. (1) yields

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{\alpha}{T} + \delta T + \gamma T^2. \quad \dots (2)$$

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* P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur, to whom all correspondence be made.

** Department of Physics, T.N.B. College, Bhagalpur.

*** Department of Chemistry, Deoghar College, Deoghar.

In equation (2), representing thermal resistivity, the first term of r.h.s., according to earlier views⁷⁻¹⁸, stands for the contribution due to geometrical factors and impurities present in the specimen, the second one is attributed to electron-electron scattering in metals, while the third one represents the effect of electron-phonon interaction. These explanations of the terms are, however, restricted to the case of metals only and they are based on the assumptions³ that (1) phonon contribution to thermal conductivity is vanishingly small, (ii) the electrons are alone responsible for thermal conductivity, and (iii) the lattice and the electronic system remain essentially in thermal equilibrium. However, the existence of thermal equilibrium of electrons at low temperatures has been strongly criticised¹⁹. A very small probability of electrons being in thermal equilibrium does not justify the dominant role of electrons in heat conduction in metals. Rather phonons appear to be more competent⁵ in this field since thermal equilibrium in phonon system is always expected due to the effect of Umklapp process²⁰ and anharmonicity²¹ of lattice forces. Anharmonic coupling of phonons, according to Klemens²¹, establishes thermal equilibrium in phonons but does not offer thermal resistance. Thus a contribution to thermal conductivity is expected due to the anharmonic coupling since in this process^{22,23} the number of phonons participating in conduction phenomenon is increased while the number of phonons forscattering of thermal phonons is reduced. Predomination of anharmonic coupling²¹ over the Umklapp process²⁰ appears to be more reasonable since the number of phonons taking part in Umklapp process²⁰ varies²⁴ as $e^{-\theta/2T}$ which is vanishingly small at sufficiently low temperatures.

According to the recent views⁵, the second term in r.h.s. of eqn. (2) may be attributed to the effect of anhrmonic coupling of phonons, the first is due to scattering of phonons by geometrical factors

including impurities and the third one is due to phonon-phonon-interaction. Contribution due to electron-electron and electron-phonon scattering has been ignored in the light of the recent developments⁶. Interpretation of the three terms in r.h.s. of eqn. (2) given above appears reasonably valid in all solids irrespective of their metallic, semimetallic and non-metallic characters including molecular crystals [cf. Table 1].

The constants α , δ and γ in eqn. (2) have been obtained from the analysis of experimentally observed thermal conductivity¹ for thirty two elements of varied nature (metals, semiconductors are insulators including molecular crystals) and also for two compounds^{25,26}. These values are shown in Table 1. The nature of each individual constant in all the thirty four cases is found to be the same which unambiguously justifies the generality of the form suggested in eqn. (1).

TABLE 1—CALCULATED VALUES OF α , δ AND γ FROM EQN. (2)

Element	α (cm.deg. / Watt.)	δ (cm. / Wat.)	γ (cm. / Watt.deg.)
1	2	3	4
Aluminium	0.03436	-0.168×10^{-4}	1.846×10^{-5}
Antimony	2.163	-1.720×10^{-2}	1.640×10^{-3}
Beryllium	0.550	-7.334×10^{-5}	0.677×10^{-5}
Boron	5.720	-1.530×10^{-3}	8.360×10^{-5}
Chromium	2.500	-1.413×10^{-4}	1.115×10^{-4}
Cobalt	3.700	-0.710×10^{-4}	1.093×10^{-4}
Copper	0.025	-9.680×10^{-5}	2.627×10^{-5}
Indium	0.042	-3.35×10^{-3}	2.400×10^{-3}
Iron	0.600	-7.000×10^{-4}	1.300×10^{-4}
Iridium	0.780	-5.00×10^{-4}	5.600×10^{-5}
Gold	0.183	-3.480×10^{-5}	1.259×10^{-4}
Lead	0.198	-4.080×10^{-2}	0.950×10^{-2}
Lithium	1.515	-0.115×10^{-2}	0.032×10^{-2}
Magnesium	0.102	-2.600×10^{-5}	7.975×10^{-5}
Molybdenum	6.590	-5.400×10^{-5}	5.140×10^{-5}
Neon	56.000	-4.000	1.500
Nickel	0.460	-3.120×10^{-4}	1.100×10^{-4}
Niobium	2.900	-2.00×10^{-2}	0.172×10^{-2}
Palladium	0.500	-9.500×10^{-4}	4.030×10^{-4}
Platinum	0.435	-14.540×10^{-4}	5.234×10^{-4}
Osmium	0.650	-5.117×10^{-4}	1.000×10^{-4}
Rhodium	0.392	-1.030×10^{-3}	7.126×10^{-5}
Ruthenium	0.873	-6.620×10^{-4}	5.950×10^{-5}
Silicon	1.340	-5.430×10^{-3}	1.550×10^{-4}
Silver	0.028	-2.240×10^{-4}	6.000×10^{-5}
Sodium	0.050	-2.700×10^{-4}	4.160×10^{-4}
Tantalum	9.000	-5.800×10^{-3}	9.250×10^{-4}
Thorium	1.100	-5.350×10^{-3}	1.600×10^{-3}
Tin	0.007	-1.211×10^{-3}	0.736×10^{-3}
Tungsten	0.0734	-4.970×10^{-4}	7.800×10^{-5}
Zinc	0.067	-2.000×10^{-3}	0.342×10^{-3}
Krypton	1.000	-12.00	7.110×10^{-1}
Quartz	0.314	-1.06×10^{-3}	0.4×10^{-3}
Synthetic Sapphire	12.573	-9.081×10^{-3}	1.0192×10^{-4}

Different sets of values of α , δ and γ which have been obtained for different metals are natural because of the fact that :

(i) Impurity content and the geometrical factors vary from specimen to specimen,

(ii) Number of thermally excited phonons at any temperature is a function of the Debye temperature θ depending upon the atomic weight and the elastic constant which have different values for different metals,

(iii) Electron-phonon and phonon-phonon interaction cross-section varies from specimen to specimen at a given temperature since the energy of excited phonons and electrons are different in different solids at the same temperature.

(iv) Magnitude of anharmonic coupling is expected to be different in different solids at a given temperature.

From eqn. (1) the expression for T_{opt} is obtained as :

$$\alpha = \delta T_{opt}^2 + 2\gamma T_{opt}^3 \quad \dots (3)$$

This cubic equation has one real and two imaginary roots. The solution of eqn. (3) for real root gives.

$$T_{opt} = (\alpha/4\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \frac{\delta^3}{54\alpha\gamma^2} \right)^{1/3} + \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \frac{\delta^3}{54\alpha\gamma^2} \right)^{1/3} \right\} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (4)$$

Since $\alpha \gg \delta$ and also because δ and γ are more or less of the same order of magnitude (c.f. Table 1), first order of approximation of eqn. (4) gives

$$T_{opt} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (5)$$

Equation (4), to the second order of approximation, gives,

$$T'_{opt} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ 1 + \frac{2^{2/3}\delta^2}{36\alpha^{2/3}\gamma^{4/3}} \right\} - \frac{\delta}{6\gamma} \quad \dots (6)$$

Equations (5) and (6) give

$$T'_{opt} - T_{opt} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ \frac{2^{2/3}\delta^2}{36\alpha^{2/3}\gamma^{4/3}} \right\} \quad \dots (7)$$

Equation (5) has been used to calculate T_{opt} for a number of elements. These values are listed in Table 2 together with the observed ones¹. The agreement between these two is very satisfactory. The value of T_{opt} with greater accuracy may be obtained by applying correction given in equation (7).

Some analysis⁶ finds $1/K\alpha T$ (approximately) in certain zone of temperature, the slope being different for different elements (Fig. 1 and 2). Such result follows from eqn. (1) when $(\alpha/T^2 + \delta + \gamma T)$ for a solid attains a constant value. The quantity $(\alpha/T^2 + \delta + \gamma T)$, if evaluated by using the values of α , δ , γ given in Table 1, is found to lie in the neighbourhood of some constant value suggesting $1/K$ to vary as T .

Fig. 1. Dependence of thermal resistivity ($1/K$) on temperature (T). [The scale and origin have been suitably altered along the axes to portray the desired shape of the curves].

Fig. 2. Same as fig. 1 but for a different set of elements.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED AND OBSERVED¹ VALUES OF T_{opt}

(T_{opt} has been calculated from eqn. (5))

Element	Values of T_{opt} in ($^{\circ}K$)	
	Calculated	Observed ¹
1	2	3
Aluminium	8.85	9
Antimony	10.45	9
Beryllium	36.50	35
Boron	35.40	30—35
Chromium	22.6	20—25
Cobalt	25.8	25
Copper	9.4	9
Indium	2.23	2
Iron	14.2	15
Iridium	20.6	20
Gold	9	9
Lead	2.157	2
Lithium	13.9	16
Magnesium	8.605	9
Neon	3.144	3.5
Nickel	13.27	13
Niobium	11.44	13
Palladium	8.54	9
Platinum	7.964	8
Osmium	15.633	20
Rhodium	16.41	18
Ruthenium	19.654	20
Silicon	22.14	25
Silver	7.16	7
Sodium	4.21	4
Tantalum	18.05	18
Thorium	7.56	8
Tin	1.97	2
Tungsten	8.762	10
Zinc	4.697	6
Krypton	10.7	10
Synthetic Sapphire	54.25	56
Quartz	7.7534	9

Physical significance of the second term in eqn. (2)

A salient feature of the second term in r.h.s. of eqn. (2) is that, even in the case of a perfect crystal of infinite dimensions, T_{opt} [c.f. eqn. (3)] is finite and greater than zero [c.f. Table 2]. Moreover, this term has an important role in explaining the temperature dependence of electrical resistivity also, in addition to thermal resistivity, at low temperatures. In this context, it is to be noted that the temperature variation of experimentally observed electrical resistivity of metals is best explained^{6,28} on the basis of the T^2 term in the expression for electrical resistivity in most of the cases at low temperatures. Some earlier authors^{11,7} have tried to explain such a temperature variation on the basis of electron-electron scattering. However, this has been criticized^{29,30} at least in simple metals in which the transition probability from s - p levels to unfilled d -level is negligibly small. The explanation of T^2 term in electrical resistivity on the basis of electron-phonon scattering appears to be logical on the following grounds :

(i) The temperature dependence of electrical resistivity may be interpreted directly in terms of the temperature variation of atomic energy⁶ since the scattering cross section of electrons with lattice vibrations is directly proportional to the mean-square displacement of the lattices and hence the atomic energy⁶, if the idea³¹ of the scattering of electrons with lattice vibrations at normal temperatures is supposed to be valid at low temperatures.

(ii) Since the temperature dependence of atomic energy of solids at low temperatures, $T < 0.3\theta$, is found to be expressible in the form⁶ $E - E_0 = CT^2 + DT^3$ where terms containing higher powers of T have been ignored since the coefficients converge rapidly. In the above expression E_0 is the energy

at temperature $T = 0$ and C and D are constants⁶. It, therefore, seems reasonable to suggest that additional phonons, due to anharmonic coupling²¹ are responsible to lead to T^2 term in the temperature dependence of electrical resistivity as they become available for scattering of electrons. Contrary to this, in the process of thermal conduction, anharmonic coupling contributes to thermal conductivity but does not offer any resistance²⁴. This is obvious from eqn. (1) in which δ , associated with negative sign [c.f. Table 1], is present in its denominator. In the case of insulators also the predomination of anharmonic coupling has been advocated by several authors^{21,22} which is in conformity with the present findings. These are in favour of having identical temperature variation^{1,5} of thermal conductivity of solids, irrespective of their metallic, semiconducting, molecular crystal and non-metallic characters, at low temperatures.

A comparative study of two term and three term equations :

A two term empirical equation, suggested earlier²⁻⁴, for thermal conductivity of metals is expressed as :

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{a}{T} + bT^2 \quad \dots (8)$$

where K is the thermal conductivity, 'a' and 'b' are the empirical constants²⁵ which vary from metal to metal and also from specimen to specimen of the same metal. a/T and b/T^2 stand for the thermal resistivity caused by scattering of electrons by geometrical factors including impurities present in the specimen and phonons, respectively.

Eqn. (8) fails to explain some experimental findings^{1,3,6} in respect of (i) linear⁵ temperature dependence of thermal resistivity in some temperature zone, (ii) variation⁶ of electrical resistivity as T^2 and (iii) to suggest the magnitudes¹ of maximum thermal conductivity, K_{max} , and optimum temperature, T_{opt} at which K_{max} occurs. T_{opt} and K_{max} have been calculated from eqns. (9) and (10) which have been obtained from eqn. (8)

$$T_{opt} = (a/2b)^{1/3} \quad \dots (9)$$

and

$$K_{max} = \left(\frac{4}{27ba^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad \dots (10)$$

These values are given in Table 3 together with experimentally observed values¹ for the sake of comparison; the disagreement in most of the cases is obvious.

Equation (8) can be based on Debye T^3 law of specific heat whose validity has been criticized^{6,32-36} in many cases.

The validity of eqn. (8) is limited to metals only.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED AND OBSERVED VALUES OF T_{opt} AND K_{max}

T_{opt} and K_{max} have been calculated from eqns. (9) and (10) respectively

Metals	T_{opt} in (°K)		K_{max} in Watt. cm. ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	
	Calcd.	Observed	Calcd.	Observed
Aluminium	15.3	9	44.392	239
Cadmium	2.3	2	67.22	409
Cobalt	33.5	25	2.828	4.7
Copper	19.1	9	36.437	249
Gold	14.4	9	8.483	32.7
Iron	36.5	15.0	2.523	17
Iridium	20.1	20	17.89	19
Magnesium	18.3	9	11.65	57
Palladium	31.2	9	1.382	11.7
Nickel	28.1	13	4.079	19.7
Platinum	7.4	8	14.105	12.9
Rhodium	18.6	18	9.00	37.3
Tin	4.6	2	25.787	323
Tantalum	25.1	18	0.6695	1.43
Tungsten	31.6	10	3.618	97.1
Silver	14.8	7	32.055	193
Niobium	38.7	13	0.455	3.14
Zinc	10.0	6	10.11	38.1
Molybdenum	35.5	35-40	35.00	3.7

Moreover, experimental evidences^{37,38} are also there to show that (i) 'b' is not a strictly constant quantity for a specimen of a metal, and (ii) the power to which T has to be raised in the second term of the said equation is also not strictly equal to two for most of the metals.

On the other hand equation (1) has the merit of being equally valid for metals, semi-conductors and insulators including molecular crystals.

Observed $K-T$ curves¹ which are more or less identical in nature⁶ {fig. 3} get explained by eqn. (1).

The calculated values of T_{opt} from eqn. (5) by making use of the constants given in Table 1 are in good agreement with the observed ones¹ [cf. Table 2].

Temperature variation⁶ of electrical resistivity of metals as T^2 also gets explained [cf. significance of 2nd term].

So far the cause of the electrical resistivity at low temperatures is concerned, eqn. (1) does not make any distinction in between simple and transition metals.

It gives a strong support to the ideas that (i) the anharmonicity^{21,22} of lattice forces are responsible for maintaining thermal equilibrium in phonon system and (ii) phonons are the main participants in conduction of thermal energy in solids, at low temperatures.

It is also an improvement over the previous three term equation⁷⁻⁹, applicable for metals only, as it has a general applicability.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the thermal conductivity (K) on temperature (T). [The origin and the magnification scale along the axes have been suitably altered to present just the desired shape of the curves].

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